

was dissolved in methanol (5 ml), 3*N* hydrochloric acid (5 ml) added and the contents were boiled for 5–10 min. Ice-cold water was then added and the solution extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated. The flavanone was obtained as a yellow coloured solid (20 mg) m.p. 148° (Found: C, 67.7; H, 6.6. C₂₁H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 67.4; H, 7.0%); λ_{max} 240 and 285 nm; ν_{max} 3 390, 1 660, 1 610, 1 575, 1 550, 1 500, 1 460, 1 380, 1 290, 1 250, 1 160, 1 040, 980, 920, 810 and 780 cm⁻¹; δ (acetone-d₆) 1.79 (6H, s, C(CH₃)₂), 2.70–2.82 (2H, m, H-3), 3.42 (5H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂-CH= and OCH₃), 4.63 (1H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂-CH=), 5.66 (1H, dd, *J* 12.5 Hz and 3.8 Hz, H-2), 6.85 (2H, s, H-3' and 5'), 7.66 (1H, s, H-2') and 12.47 (1H, s, OH).

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Azomethines and Thiazolidinone Derivatives of Benzimidazoles

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BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial¹⁻³, insecticidal⁴, fungicidal⁵, virucidal⁶ and antiparasitic^{7,8} activities. Several thiazolidinone derivatives are found to possess diverse biological properties, viz. fungicidal⁹, antibacterial¹⁰, anticonvulsant¹¹ and amoebicidal¹². In continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinones¹³ possessing heterocyclic moieties, we report here the synthesis and antibacterial activity of some azomethines and thiazolidinone derivatives with benzimidazole moiety in a single molecular framework.

The key intermediate, 2-*N*-(*p*-aminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1) was refluxed with different arylaldehydes in absolute ethanol in the presence of acetic acid to get the desired 2-*N*-(*p*-arylidene-aminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazoles (2) which undergo cyclocondensation with

mercaptoacetic acid to furnish 2-*p*-(2-aryl-4-oxothiazolin-3-yl) phenyl / diphenylaminomethylbenzimidazole (3). Structure of compounds 2 and 3 were established on the basis of their elemental analyses and ir spectra. Compound 2 gave important bands at 3 280–3 310 (N–H stretch), 1 600–1 625 (C=N azomethines) and 1 360–1 375 cm⁻¹ (pentacyclic ring). Spectra of compound 3 gave peaks at 3 285–3 310 (N–H), 2 905–2 950 (CH₂), 1 630–1 655 (C=O) and 1 250–1 310 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid bath in open capillary and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 377 spectrophotometer. Tlc was done on silica gel plates.

2-*N*-(*p*-Aminophenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1): 2-Chloromethylbenzimidazole¹⁴ (0.01 mol) and 1,4-diaminobenzene (0.01 mol) were refluxed in dry benzene for 4 h, and then excess benzene was distilled off. The separated solid was washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 162° (Found: N, 23.48. C₁₄H₁₄N₄ requires: N, 23.52%).

Similarly, 2-*N*-(*p*-aminodiphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1b) was obtained, m.p. 192° (Found: N, 17.80, C₂₀H₁₈N₄ requires: N, 17.83%).

2-*N*-(*p*-Arylideneaminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), arylaldehyde (0.01 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting mixture was cooled and poured over

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a - m AND 3a - u*

Compd. no.		n	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Yield %
2a	2-Furyl	1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	150d	65
2b	2-Hydroxyphenyl	1	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	165	70
2c	4-N,N-Diethylaminophenyl	1	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂	158	72
2d	4-N,N-Diethylaminophenyl	1	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂	130	66
2e	2-Methyl-3-hydroxyphenyl	1	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	170	65
2f	2-Furyl	2	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	>250	68
2g	Phenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂	228	70
2h	2-Nitrophenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	198	65
2i	2-Hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	250	75
2j	4-Hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	236	72
2k	N,N-Dimethylphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂	250	70
2l	N,N-Diethylaminophenyl	2	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂	230	68
2m	2-Methyl-3-hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	172	65
3a	2-Furyl	1	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	>260	65
3b	2 Hydroxyphenyl	1	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	136d	70
3c	4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl	1	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	250	69
3d	4-N,N-Diethylaminophenyl	1	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	182	65
3e	2-Methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl	1	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	148	70
3f	2-Furyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	>250	65
3g	Phenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	>250	68
3h	2-Nitrophenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	204	60
3i	2-Hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	176	63
3j	4-Hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	145	65
3k	N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl	2	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	225	70
3l	N,N-Diethylaminophenyl	2	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	190	69
3m	2-Methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl	2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	140	60

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses, and were recrystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a - m AND 3a - k

Compd. no.	Antibacterial activity*				Fungicidal activity*			
	B.s.	B.c.	S.l.	S.a.	% Inhibition of A.a.		% Inhibition of A.n.	
					dilution 1 : 200	1 : 5000	dilution 1 : 2500	1 : 5050
2a	+++	+++	+++	++	80	48	70	68
2b	+++	+++	+++	+++	71	60	60	78
2c	+++	+++	+++	++	60	63	50	65
2d	+++	++	+++	+++	43	40	30	45
2e	+++	+++	+++	+++	78	43	73	65
2f	+++	++	+++	++	87	74	68	62
2g	+++	++	+++	++	74	78	72	68
2h	+++	++	+++	++	30	60	39	45
2i	+++	++	+++	++	78	87	75	36
2j	++	++	+++	++	83	93	70	69
2k	++	++	+++	++	67	87	86	80
3a	+++	+++	+++	++	37	85	40	65
3b	+++	+++	+++	+++	64	87	60	55
3c	+++	+++	+++	+++	56	93	65	48
3d	+++	++	+++	+++	39	67	40	45
3e	+++	+++	+++	+++	83	60	48	55
3f	+++	++	+++	++	78	93	75	60
3g	+++	++	+++	++	74	78	70	75
3h	+++	++	+++	++	60	67	60	72
3i	+++	++	+++	++	38	60	40	55
3j	++	++	+++	++	37	66	56	70
3k	++	++	+++	++	71	56	70	80
Tetracycline (standard)	20 mm	36 mm	24 mm	24 mm				

* Zone (+)=6-8 mm, (++)=9-16 mm, (+++)=17-25 mm.

** B.s.=*B. subtilis*, B.c.=*B. cereus*, S.l.=*S. lutea*, S.a.=*S. aureus*, A.a.=*A. alternata*, A.n.=*A. niger*.

crushed ice. The coloured solid product obtained was washed several times with water and then recrystallised from ethanol. The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

2-p-(2-Aryl-4-oxothiazolin-3-yl)phenyl/diphenyl-aminomethylbenzimidazole (3): A mixture of 2 (0.015 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.015 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 4-5 h. Excess

benzene was then distilled off and the resulting solid washed with aqueous 10% sodium carbonate solution and finally recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity of all the synthesised compounds, 2a-k and 3a-k except 2e, m and 3l were screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Sarcina lutea* by the agar-plate-diffusion technique¹⁵. The standard antibacterial drug used was tetracycline. A standard 5 mm diameter sterilised filter paper disc impregnated with the compound (1 mg ml⁻¹ of acetone) was placed on an agar-plate seeded with test organism. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°. The zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc was observed. The screening results are given in Table 2, indicated that all the compounds exhibited antibacterial activities less than the standard used. The antibacterial activities of azomethines 2a-k are comparable to their cyclised products thiazolidinones 3a-k. No structure-activity relationship could be established, since the degree of inhibition produced by azomethines and thiazolidines were fairly constant.

Fungicidal activity: All the compounds (2a-k and 2a-k) were screened for fungicidal activity on *Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus niger* at different dilutions. The results are summarised in Table 2. The fungicidal screening was carried out by determining the percentage inhibition of colonial growth in comparison to the growth in control¹⁶. All solutions were prepared in acetone and the medium in the treated plates was potato dextrose agar culture medium and the incubation time was 96 h at 28 ± 1°. From Table 2 it is evident that the compounds 2 and 3 are capable of inhibiting fungal growth to a considerable extent both at high and low dilutions.

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Chemical Constituents of *Citrullus colocynthis*

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FRUITS of *Citrullus colocynthis*, a medicinal plant of desert region¹⁻⁴, were collected from different areas of Jodhpur district for the present study. The fruit coat was initially separated from the pulp. Both fruit coat and the pulp were extracted separately in soxhlet with benzene and ethyl acetate successively. The extracts were distilled and the gummy residues chromatographed over silica gel in separate columns. Elution of the benzene extract of the fruit coat with petrol-benzene (85 : 15) gave a compound, which on crystallisation from hot acetone gave a pure compound (A). m.p. 69°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2920, 2830, 1472, 1385, 1305, 735 and 720 cm⁻¹; δ 0.95 and 1.2. It was found identical with hentriacontane (m.m.p. and ir)^{5,6}. Elution of the benzene extract of fruit pulp with petrol-benzene (80 : 20) also furnished the same compound (A), which was found identical with hentriacontane (m.m.p. and ir).

The chromatogram on further elution with benzene-methanol (90 : 10 and 80 : 20) yielded two compounds (C and D), which were separated with plc. The compound C was crystallised with methanol, m.p. 82-83°, M^+ 514 (Found : C, 69.76 ; H, 8.13. C₃₀H₄₂O₇ requires : C, 70.03 ; H, 7.78%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 1686, 1660, 1620, 1413, 1248, 1141, 1080, 985 and 870 cm⁻¹ ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (EtOH) 230 (4.2) and 270 nm (2.2). It was found identical with elateridine in its reactions, ir and uv, but its m.p. (82-3°) was much lower than that reported (134-35°) for elateridine.

Compound D was crystallised to furnish a solid, m.p. 116°, M^+ 400 (Found : C, 71.87 ; H, 8.12. C₂₄H₃₂O₅ requires : C, 72.00 ; H, 8.03%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 3350, 1715, 1690, 1660, 1587, 1385, 1040, 980 and 970 cm⁻¹ ; $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (EtOH) 240 (3.5) and 270 (1.6) ; δ 5.9 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz), 5.7 (1H, m), 5.0 (1H, m), 2.22 (3H, s), 0.9-1.2 (15 H). Acetylation with Py-Ac₂O (at room temperature) gave monoacetate, m.p. 140°, M^+ 442 (Found : C, 70.54 ; H, 7.72 ; CH₃CO, 9.20. C₂₆H₃₄O₆ requires : C, 70.58 ; H, 7.69 ; CH₃CO (1 acetyl group), 9.72%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3350, 1740, 1720, 1690, 1660, 1589.

* 55 Bhagat-ki-kothi Extension Scheme, Jodhpur-342 003.